

Oral Health of Elite Athletes – Data Collection Sheet

SUBJECT NUMBER

AGE

GENDER

EXAMINATION DATE

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EXAMINER NUMBER

INTERNATIONAL CARIES DETECTION AND ASSESSMENT SYSTEM II (ICDAS II)

	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11		21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
CROWN Score 1	<input style="width: 30px; height: 25px;" type="text"/>		<input style="width: 30px; height: 25px;" type="text"/>														
CROWN Score 2	<input style="width: 30px; height: 25px;" type="text"/>		<input style="width: 30px; height: 25px;" type="text"/>														
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CROWN Score 2	<input style="width: 30px; height: 25px;" type="text"/>		<input style="width: 30px; height: 25px;" type="text"/>														

Coronal ICDAS SCORE I

- 0 = surface not restored or sealed
- 1 = Sealant, partial
- 2 = Sealant, full
- 3 = Tooth coloured restoration
- 4 = Amalgam restoration
- 5 = Stainless steel crown
- 6 = Porcelain or fold or PFM crown or veneer
- 7 = Lost or broken restoration
- 8 = Temporary restoration
- 96= Tooth surface cannot be examined
- 97: Tooth missing because of caries
- 98: Tooth missing for reasons other than caries
- 99: Unerupted

Coronal ICDAS SCORE II

- 0 = Sound
- 1 = First visual change in enamel
- 2 = Distinct visual change in enamel
- 3 = Localised enamel breakdown (without clinical visual signs of dentinal involvement)
- 4 = Underlying dark shadow from dentine
- 5 = Distinct cavity with visible dentine
- 6 = Extensive distinct cavity with visible dentine

BASIC EROSIVE WEAR EXAMINATION (BEWE)

17-14	13-23	24-27
47-44	43-33	34-37

TOOTH WEAR

- Score worst tooth per sextant
- 0 = No erosive tooth wear
- 1 = Initial loss of surface texture (enamel)
- 2 = Distinct defect, hard tissue loss <50% of surface area (dentine)
- 3 = Hard tissue loss >50% of the surface area
- X - Sextant excluded

BASIC PERIODONTAL EXAMINATION (BPE)

17-14	13-23	24-27
47-44	43-33	34-37

BPE (using a WHO probe)

Score worst tooth per sextant

- 0 = Probing depth <3.5mm, no calculus/overhangs, no bleeding on probing (black band entirely visible)
- 1 = Probing depth <3.5mm, no calculus/overhangs, bleeding on probing (black band entirely visible)
- 2 = Probing depth <3.5mm, supra or subgingival calculus/overhangs (black band entirely visible)
- 3 = Probing depth 3.5-5.5mm (black band partially visible, indicating pocket of 4-5mm)
- 4 = Probing depth >5.5mm (black band disappears, indicating a pocket of 6mm or more)
- * = furcation

TRAUMA (WHO)

Status	
Number of teeth affected	

WHO trauma status

- 0 = No sign of injury
- 1 = Treated injury
- 2 = Enamel fracture only
- 3 = Enamel and dentine fracture
- 4 = Pulp involvement
- 5 = Missing tooth due to trauma
- 6 = Other damage
- 9 = Excluded tooth

PULP, ULCERATION, FISTULA AND ABSCESS INDEX (PUFA)

UR	UL
LR	LL

PUFA

- Score each quadrant as 0,1,2
- 0 = no lesions evident
 - 1 = a single lesion present
 - 2 = 2 or more lesions present

PUFA

- P = open pulp in permanent dentition
- U = obvious ulceration
- F = fistula in permanent dentition
- A = abscess in permanent dentition

WISDOM TEETH

	Y	N
Removal?		
Pain?		
Infection?		

TEMPOROMANDIBULAR ASSESSMENT

	Y	N
Pain?		
Limited opening?		